

PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION AND ITS CLASSIFICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The problem of translation is one of the main areas of linguistics. There are a number of types and methods of translation. It is important to be able to use them correctly and follow the rules. This article discusses the basics of translation, its methods, cases of application and gives examples.

INTRODUCTION

Translation is an important tool that provides spiritual communication with the peoples of the world. While the requirements for translation are updated over time, its creative character, the art of re-creation, remains unchanged. The extent and progress of translation depends on the educational level and spiritual level of each nation, and, in turn, it effectively affects the social thinking of the nation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

V. Komissarov, A. Fyodorov, L. Barhudarov, Y. Retsker, F. Salomov, K. Musayev, Y. Nayda, J. Catford and others made a great contribution to the development and theory formation of translation studies.

Ghaybulla al-Salam has a great place in Uzbek translation studies, and his treatises such as "Translation of proverbs, proverbs and idioms", "Lexical and phraseological issues of artistic translation", "Translation of proverbs and proverbs from Russian to Uzbek" , as well as the monograph "Language and translation", although it was the first work of the professor, made a fundamental change in translation studies. [1]

Today, many Uzbek translators and linguists are contributing to modern translation studies of the 21st century. Khurshid Davron, Muhammad Ali, Ibrahim Gafurov, Qudratkhan Musayev, Abduzokhur Abduazizov, Najmiddin Komilov, Begoyim Kholbekova are examples of them.

Furthermore, Malcolm Marsh says: "Translation is a two-part exercise involving understanding and expression. Understanding requires deep knowledge of the original language in order to perceive the meanings at different levels and also to be familiar with the content area of the text. Expression is the ability to reproduce what is understood in the original language in the translated language as accurately and reliably as possible and at the same time preserving the style of the original language." [4]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Catford divides translation into types according to extent, level and rank. According to the extent: full and partial; according to the level: total and restricted; ranks (rank-bound vs unbounded translation).

In full translation, the entire language is involved in the translation process and all parts of the original language are replaced by the material in the translated language.

In partial translation, some parts of the original language are left untranslated, they are simply transferred and inserted into the target language. This type of translation is mainly used when there are "untranslatable units" or to preserve the local color of the original language.

Catford also introduced three famous types of translation: word-for-word translation, free translation and literal translation. He defines these translation types as follows:

"Word-for-word translation generally means what it says: i.e. is essentially rank-bound at word-rank (but may include some morphemes-morphemes equivalences).

Free translation is always unbounded—equivalences shunt up and down the rank scale, but tends to be at the higher ranks—sometimes between larger units than the sentence.

Literal translation is between word-for-word translation and free translation. It may start, as it were, from a word-for-word translation, but make changes in conformity with TL grammar (e.g. inserting additional word, changing structure at any rank, etc.); this may make it a group-group or clause-clause translation". [2 p.25]

Literal translation is mainly used when the grammatical structure of the original and translated languages is the same. The reason is that grammatical changes do not occur in such situations.

Free translation - more closely follows the structure of the translation language, some parts of the original source may be changed or corrupted.

Below we will consider the types of translations found in Robert T. Kiyosaki's work "Rich Dad, Poor Dad" and his Uzbek translation " Boy ota, kambag'al ota" by Mirafzal Mirfayziyev:

To parents everywhere, a child's first and most important teachers, and to all those who educate, influence, and lead by example [6]

Ushbu kitob farzandlarining eng asosiy o'qituvchilari - butun dunyo ota- onalariga bag'ishlanadi. [7]

In this example, the free translation method was used, and the main content of the sentence was translated into Uzbek.

The love of money is the root of all evil. [6P:2]

Love of money is the root of all problems. [7p:21]

As a young boy, having two strong fathers both influencing me was difficult. [6p:2]

It was difficult for me, a young man, because I had two fathers who had a strong influence. [7p:21]

In the above examples, the method of ideomatic translation was used, and only the arrangement of words was adapted to the Uzbek language.

The lack of money is the root of all evil. [6 P:2]

Pulning yetishmasligi barcha ofatlarning boshlanishidir. [7 p:21]

In this example, the free translation method is used.

My soon-to-be-rich dad would explain that by automatically saying the words "I can't afford it," your brain stops working. [6 p:3]

CONCLUSION

In these examples, the translator used the free translation method.

From the above examples, we can come to the conclusion that literal translation was not used in the translation into English and Uzbek. The reason for this is that English and Uzbek languages are not related to each other, so their grammatical structure is fundamentally different from each other.

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